

Impulsivity and Driver Stress in Mexico and Spain

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Abstract. Driver stress has been a topic of interest in recent years. The search for the promotion of human well-being has described different factors that work against it. Human impulsivity is not only described as a personality trait, it also has been linked to behavior difficulties and psychological effects, such as stress. This study aimed to determine the influence of impulsivity in driver stress in Mexico and Spain, to help determine psychological factors that hinder human experience. A sample of 1500 individuals from both countries was comprised, and then relevant statistical analyses were carried out to determine relationships between variables. It was found that impulsivity is a strong factor in driver stress in both countries, and that there are no differences between countries. Only women suffer more driver stress than men, yet all other demographic variables remain stable across analyses.

Keywords: Stress, Impulsivity, Traffic Psychology, CFA

Introduction

Driver stress is a phenomenon that has been studied for some years now. Since Hans Selye (1978) defined the relationship between the individual and the adaptation to its environment, and then Richard Lazarus & Susan Folkman (1984) describe the way in which human being elaborate stress through what things mean to their well-being. This has given way to a plethora of studies involving stress and parenting skills (Ajilchi et al., 2011), teacher experience (Onen & Ulusoy, 2015), violence in urban settings (Rocha-Rego et al., 2012), quality of life (Rinaldis et al., 2012), and of course, Traffic Psychology (Clapp et al., 2014; Hennessy & Wiesenthal, 1999; Montoro et al., 2018). It would appear that stress has become one of social sciences main concern regarding individual's well-being in many different aspects of everyday life (Dijkstra et al., 2011; Khan & Saleem, Muhammad, Shahid, 2012; Park et al., 2012; Segerstrom & O'Connor, 2012).

Impulsivity is defined as a natural predisposition an individual has towards rapid reactions or unplanned behavior as a response to internal or external stimuli that lacks hindsight towards negative consequences or risks (Shin et al., 2016). Some consider it to be a personality trait (Maneiro et al., 2017; Swann et al., 2009, 2011), and is found to be related to depression (Vaz-Leal et al., 2014), substance use (Egan et al., 2010; Sargeant et al., 2012), and driving (Pearson et al., 2013). Impulsivity, as a personality trait, has been known to be related to antisocial personality disorder (Hahn et al., 2016; Swann et al., 2009, 2011), and sensation-seeking (Zuckerman & Glicksohn, 2016), amongst many others. If impulsivity is a trait, then it should influence aspects of life that are based on fast and diverse interactions with others and the environment, such as driving a motor-vehicle.

What are the forces behind driver stress? Is driver stress purely circumstantial? Are there variables of a psychological nature that fuel driver stress? Is impulsivity a factor behind driver

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stress? This study had as its main objective to determine if impulsivity influences driver stress in Mexico and Spain. It is hypothesized that impulsivity will influence driver stress in both countries. To this end, two scales were selected, a sample of people from Mexico and Spain drawn, and relevant statistical analyses were carried out.

Methods

Procedure

A multiple format procedure was used for this study. Most of the sample was acquired through a pen and paper format, a pdf file was sent to collaborators which was then printed out and used to collect data through students and volunteers. To further the sample, the instrument was keyed into a SurveyMonkey link, which was then forwarded to collaborators, students, and volunteers. Informed consent was also collected in this manner, following ethical guidelines (Aguilera-Guzmán et al., 2008; Mondragón-Barrios, 2009). The data collection period lasted about three months. This paper attempts to provide construct validity (Cohen & Swerdlik, 2009; Hair et al., 1999) for one of the three instruments here presented, as well as statistical analyses regarding convergent validity (Cohen & Swerdlik, 2009). Analyses were carried out on the SPSS v. 19 and the AMOS module for the same software v. 20, as well as Software R v. 3.4.3.

Sample

A total of 1552 individuals participated in this study, 52.3% of them were male and 47.3% were female. The most frequent occupations were student (19.2%), salesperson (4.7%), teacher (3.5%), employee (3.4%), and housework (3%). Two main countries were targeted for the sample: Mexico (70.4%), and Spain (27.9%). Age mean was 35.17 years of age (std. dev. 13.07). The mean for years of scholastic instruction was 14.84 (std. dev. 3.81).

Instruments

Two instruments were used for this study. Driver Stress was evaluated through the LatinSET (Dorantes Argandar et al., 2020), which evaluates said variable through a 9 item Likert-style scale that evaluates how much stress some elements encountered during driving stress the driver (1 = not stressful, 5 = very stressful). Said scale is divided into two factors: Outside the Car, and Inside the Car. Its original publication yielded a Cronbach's Alpha of .86, and this study yielded a .9, which indicates a high level of internal consistency.

The second instrument was the Impulsive Behavior Inventory (ICI), which was validated in Mexican drivers (Dorantes-Argandar & Ferrero-Berlanga, 2016). Said inventory evaluates how impulsive an individual is through a 10 item Likert-style scale in a one-factor alignment that indicates how impulsively an individual is (1 = never, 5 = always). Revalidation analyses were warranted because this sample was carried out in Mexican and Spanish participants.

Results

The ICI required validation analysis due to the nature of the sample obtained. For this purpose, the sample was divided in two using the SPSS's random assigning feature, and an Exploratory Factorial Analysis was carried out in the first half, and the other half was used for the Confirmatory Factorial Analysis, which was carried out on the AMOS. All 10 items were included in the first analysis, although only 5 items obtained communalities above .4. This 5 item scale is aligned in a single factor that explains 65.8% of variance, all items correlate significantly with each other, the scale has a KMO of .85, passed Bartlett's Test of Sphericity ($X^2 = 3603.42$ (10), $p \leq .001$), and had an excellent model fit ($X^2 = 104.82$ (5) $p \leq .001$). Factor loadings can be observed in Table 1.

Table 1. Factor Loadings for the LatinCI

#	Item	Factor Loading	Communality
IMP5	I find it hard to wait for someone or something.	.67	.45
IMP6	I am easily angered.	.79	.63
IMP7	I find other people frustrating.	.71	.51
IMP9	I am easily exasperated.	.84	.7
IMP10	I find it hard to tolerate other people.	.77	.6

The confirmatory factorial analysis was then carried out on this factorial alignment and can be found in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Confirmatory Factorial Analysis for the LatinCI

This factorial structure achieved minimum requirements of fit ($X^2 = 105.68(5)$, $p \leq .001$). It also held excellent levels of model fit (CFI = .97 TLI = .92 RMSEA = .1) (Escobedo-Portillo et al., 2016; Ruiz et al., 2010).

Indexes for each variable were then composed, and correlations were drawn. Analyses indicate that Driver Stress is related to Impulsivity ($r = .48$, $p \leq .001$), and that Impulsivity predicts Driver Stress ($R^2 = .23$, $F = 456.65$, $p \leq .001$, $\beta = .48$). No other significant correlations could be found. Women seem to stress more than men ($t = 1.93(1525)$, $p \leq .001$), although no differences could be found in Impulsivity. No differences were found in nationality as well.

Discussion

Impulsivity is a force behind Driver Stress, at least in Mexico and Spain. The working hypothesis for this study has been accepted, not without some additional comments. It was expected that Impulsivity predicted Driver Stress because of its nature as a trait (Maneiro et al., 2017; Pearson et al., 2013; Swann et al., 2009; Upton et al., 2011), which actually helps in said notion. If impulsive drivers suffer more driver stress, it is because of the influence of psychological factors in the matter. Other psychological factors that are associated to impulsivity are psychopathy (Poythress & Hall, 2011; Snowden & Gray, 2011), aggression (Campbell & Muncer, 2009), depression and bulimia (Vaz-Leal et al., 2014), substance abuse (Ozten et al., 2015; Ross et al., 2013; Tziortzis et al., 2011), as well as many others. Driver stress has been found related to driver aggression (Lajunen & Parker, 2001), and work stress and fatigue (Montoro et al., 2018; Useche et al., 2017), amongst others. Evidence produced here and elsewhere strongly suggest that driver stress is influenced by various psychological and personality factors, which in turn suggests that if one desires to face the effects that driving

has on a human being, one must acknowledge the psychological nature of the factors that have influence in it.

This study also supports the notion that impulsivity is a personality trait that has strong influence on many aspects of human life, including driving a motor vehicle (Lattimore et al., 2011; Maneiro et al., 2017; Pearson et al., 2013; Swann et al., 2009; Upton et al., 2011). The fact that the LatinCI held excellent levels of fit adjustment across cultures strongly helps in this direction. It would seem that impulsivity is a driving factor behind human behavior, all the way to driver stress. This study provides construct and convergent validity (Cohen & Swerdlik, 2009; Hair et al., 1999) for said instrument, and its 5 item structure is now valid for use in Mexico and Spain. This new tool should help in developing new studies that aim to determine the influence impulsivity has on other phenomena studied through quantitative research.

As with all studies, this one has its limitations as well. The sample was not equal for both countries, which might have played a factor in not finding any differences across cultures, although statistical standards for samples and analyses were met. Additionally, only two Spanish-speaking countries were included in this study. Although this methodology has proven significant results in multicultural studies (Dorantes Argandar et al., 2020; Dorantes-Argandar et al., 2022), this study only included two countries. A more extensive research effort should be made to determine if results found here are replicated elsewhere.

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